

WEST-SLAVONIC (POLISH, CZECH, SLOVAKIAN) MALE PROPER NAMES, DERIVED FROM A ROMAN MYTHOLOGICAL NAME

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Abstract: *The research object of the present text is 3 Polish, 11 Slovakian, and 6 Czech male anthroponyms, derived from 22 Roman mythological names. The main aims are to present the list of the analyzed anthroponyms and to speak on their meanings. The researched anthroponyms are divided into two major groups according to: 1) the type of the basic word, used during the process of name derivation, as a part of speech; 2) the type formed from a Roman mythological name, i. e. if the West-Slavonic anthroponym is derived from its form of Nom. sg. or from its root. Additional extralinguistic classification is made according to the canonization of the researched names, i. e. if it is a name of a saint, and, if the saint is canonized only by the Orthodox Church, by the Catholic one, or by both of them.*

Keywords: *West-Slavonic proper name, Roman mythological name, root, anthroponym.*

1. Introduction

The research object of the present text is 3 Polish, 11 Slovakian, and 6 Czech male anthroponyms, derived from 22 Roman mythological names¹. The main aims of the present research are to identify a list of anthroponyms and to speak on their initial meanings.

There are a series of sources of information where the analyzed anthroponyms have been found. These are *Мифы народов мира (Энциклопедия в двух томах)*, т. 1 (А-К) (Myths of the Peoples of the World, v. 1 (A-K)), *Мифы народов мира (Энциклопедия в двух томах)*, т. 2 (К-Я) (Myths of the Peoples of the World, v. 2 (K-Z)), and *Oxford Latin Dictionary*. The internet sites <http://www.behindthename.com> and <http://www.kurufin.narod.ru/> have been used, too.

All the additional sources of information are listed in section *References* at the very end of the text.

The researched anthroponyms are divided into two major groups according to: 1) the type of the basic word, used during the process of name derivation, as a part of speech; 2) the model used for anthroponym coining from a Roman mythological name, i. e. if the West-Slavonic male proper

¹These names are: names of saints, canonized by the Catholic Church (for example *Romulus*), names of saints, canonized by the Orthodox Church (*Iupiter/Iuppiter/Jupiter/Juppiter; Mars/Mavors; Volcanus/Vulcanus* etc.), names of saints, canonized by the Catholic Church as well as the Orthodox one (*Honor/Honos, Mercurius/Mircurius/Mircurius, Saturnus, Silvanus* etc.).

name is derived from the form of Nom. sg. of the basic Roman one or from its root.

Additional extralinguistic classification is made according to the canonization of the researched names, i. e. if it is a name of a saint, and, if the saint is canonized only by the Orthodox Church, by the Catholic one, or by both of them.

2. Classification of the Male Roman Mythological Names According to the Type of the Used Basic Word as a Part of Speech During Their Derivation

(a) Names, derived from a common noun:

- *Honor/Honos* (<*honor, oris*, m - "honour" [6]) > *Honor* (SLK, CZ²);
- *Ianus/Janus* (<*ianus, i*, m - "arch", "door" [7]) > *Janus* (PL¹³);
- *Silvanus* (<*silva, ae, f* - "forest" [7], [8], [9]) > *Sylwan* (PL), *Silvan* (SLK, CZ).

(b) Names, derived from an adjective:

- *Latinus* (<*latinus*, 3 - "Latin" [3]) > *Latinus* (SLK);
- *Leber/Liber* (<*liber, era, erum* - "free; independent" [3]) > *Liber* (SLK), *Libor* (CZ);
- *Mars/Mavors* (<*maris* (form for Gen. sg. of *mas, maris* - "masculine") [8]) > *Mars* (SLK);
- *Romulus* (<*romulus*, 3 - "something/someone that belongs to Rome" [8]) > *Romulus* (SLK), *Romul* (CZ).

(c) Names, derived from more than one basic word:

- *Iupiter/Iuppiter/ Jupiter/ Juppiter* (< ((1) Indo-European **Dyeu-pater* (< *Dyeus/ dieu* - "god" and *pater, tri*, m - "father") meaning "father of gods/ light" (nominative sentence < common noun + common noun) [8]; (2) Etruscan *dyeu-pater* (< *dyeus* ("shadow" or "sky") and *pater* - "father") (nominative sentence < common noun + common noun) [1]; (3) *iuvo*, 1 - "to help" [7]) > *Jupiter* (SLK);
- *Mercurius/ Mircurius/ Mirqurius* (< (1) *mercor*, 1 - "to trade"; (2) *merx, mercis*, f - "goods" [7]; (3) *merces, edis*, f - "salary" [8]) > *Merkur* (SLK);
- *Remus* (< ((1) meaning unknown [8]; (2) *remus, i*, m - "oar" [3]) > *Remus* (SLK, CZ);
- *Saturnus* (< ((1) meaning unknown [8]; (2) *satur, ura, urum* - "fertile" [4]; (3) *sero*, 1 - "sow" (verb) [7]; (4) *sator, oris*, m - "sower" (common noun) [5]) > *Saturn* (PL), *Saturnus* (SLK), *Saturn* (CZ);
- *Volcanus/Vulcanus* (< ((1) *fulgo*, 3/ *fulgeo*, 2 - "to flash over" [8]; (2) Etruscan *vulca* - "wolf" [2]) > *Vulkan* (SLK).

3. Classification of the Male West-Slavonic Proper Names, Derived from a Roman Mythological One, according to the Model Used in Their Derivation

(a) Male West-Slavonic proper names, derived from a male Roman mythological one:

²SLK - Slovakian, CZ - Czech, PL - Polish.

- *Honor* (SLK, CZ) < *Honor*;
- *Janus* (PL) < *Ianus/Janus*;
- *Jupiter* (SLK) < *Iupiter/Iuppiter/Jupiter/Juppiter*;
- *Latinus* (SLK) < *Latinus*;
- *Liber* (SLK), *Libor* (CZ) < *Liber*;
- *Mars* (SLK) < *Mars/Mavors*;
- *Remus* (SLK, CZ) < *Remus*;
- *Romulus* (SLK) < *Romulus*;
- *Saturnus* (SLK) < *Saturnus*.

(b) Male West-Slavonic proper names, derived from the *root* of a Roman mythological one:

- *Merkúr* (SLK) < *Mercurius*;
- *Romul* (CZ) < *Romulus*;
- *Saturn* (PL, CZ) < *Saturnus*;
- *Sylwan* (PL), *Siloán* (SLK, CZ) < *Silvanus*;
- *Vulkán* (SLK) < *Volcanus/Vulcanus*.

4. Conclusions

More numerous are Slovakian male proper names, derived from Roman mythological names, compared with the Czech (6 in number) and Polish (3 in number) ones.

Most of the male West-Slavonic anthroponyms are derived from more than one basic word. The number of anthroponyms coined from a common noun is small. The result is a logical one, because Roman mythological names, used as a basis during the process of derivation of the male West-Slavonic proper names, are very ancient and their certain origin is unclear and their initial meaning is forgotten.

There are two models of coining a West-Slavonic proper name from a Roman mythological one. First, the name derives directly from the form Nom. sg. of the Roman mythological name, and second, the West-Slavonic anthroponym derives from its root. The first model of formation is more productive, that is why it is much more analyzed by the scientists.

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